

How search engines frame political initiatives

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1. Introduction

In this study, we analyse how the most used search engine, Google, frames the two federal popular initiatives in Switzerland: the Pensions Initiative [March 2024] and the Environmental Responsibility Initiative [February 2025]. We use a three-part process: 1) a survey among Swiss internet users (N=1,100) to identify what search queries in three main national languages they use regarding the initiatives; 2) a virtual agent-based algorithm audit to collect first page of Google results using these queries; 3) a transformer-based automated content analysis to identify generic news frames present in search results regarding the initiatives. Generic news frames (Semetko & Valkenburg, 2000), are universal patterns of information representation used by media organisations to make certain aspects of social reality more salient. The way the initiative is framed can influence its perception by the voters, which is of particular relevance for direct democracies like Switzerland, and can unequally promote the interests of political parties associated with these initiatives. Our initial analysis highlights profound differences in the distribution of generic news frames in Google's coverage of the initiatives, with the variation depending on the query's language. It raises questions about its normative implications, e.g. should Google algorithms balance such representation considering potentially unequal volume of news supply between the initiatives? What are the expectations of Google's representation of political matters in multilingual countries like Switzerland, where different language groups risk being exposed to radically different framings of the same issue? And are there certain political positions which Google is more likely to legitimise, and if so, then why and which political groups can it politically benefit?

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3. References

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